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Morphological Characterization of the Variety of Hybrid Cocoa Beans (porcelain and criollo), Cultivated in the South Zone of Lake Maracaibo, Venezuela

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Abstract

The quality of the chocolate depends, among other factors, on the cocoa bean used as raw material, where the morphological characteristics of length, width and weight of the bean are important indicators for its selection. This research carried out a sample statistical analysis that allowed obtaining a size distribution profile of the grains of the hybrid variety of Criollo cocoa and porcelain cocoa cultivated in the southern area of the lake; obtaining that the distribution of weights and dimensions of the seeds were adjusted to normal or Gaussian distributions. The average weight of the bean was $1.5105 \text{ g} \pm 0.2714 \text{ g}$, with an average length and width of the hybrid cocoa beans of $2.3590 \text{ cm} \pm 0.2259 \text{ cm}$ and $1.3694 \text{ cm} \pm 0.1152 \text{ cm}$, respectively.

Keywords: cocoa, chocolate, bean morphology

Introduction

The cocoa bean offers a unique and intense flavor that has been enjoyed since time immemorial; constituting a healthy, nutritious and natural source of energy that promotes good health (Álvarez, 2022). The dry fermented cocoa bean is the essential raw material for the production of chocolate and its uses have been extended to the pharmaceutical, confectionery and chocolate industry. In addition, it is the seat of an agro-industry with global economic and social connections. The cocoa bean is the fruit of *Theobroma cacao* L; perennial tree native to the tropical region of South America. It belongs to the order Malvales, family Malvaceae and genus *Theobroma*. Its name comes from the Greek, Theos and Bromos, which mean "food of the gods" (Soares, 2022). The seeds of *Theobroma cacao* they were used by the pre-Columbian civilizations of the Aztecs who inhabited the central part of Mexico, the Incas who occupied the western part of South America (Peru, Ecuador, Colombia and Bolivia) and the Mayans; that covered the region of the tropical forests of the current cities of Mexico, Guatemala and Honduras. Which used it not only as a food ingredient (drinks, mixed with cornmeal and spices) but also as currency for commercial exchange or rituals (ICCO, s.f)

Its world production was estimated at more than 4.8 million tons in 2021/2022 (Soares, 2023) and the main cocoa-producing countries for the same period were: Ivory Coast, Ghana, Indonesia, Nigeria, Cameroon and Brazil (Gutiérrez-Ríos, 2022).

Cocoa beans have traditionally been classified into the varieties: "fine or aroma", where Criollo and Trinitario cocoa are found and "in bulk" where Forastero cocoa stands out; which represents 95% of world production (Gutiérrez-Ríos, 2022). Although the main factors influencing the quality attributes of cocoa beans are the variety and the genotype of the tree, it

Figure 1. Postharvest stages of the cocoa bean. (A) After harvesting, the cocoa pod is broken, collected and placed in a wooden box for fermentation. (B) Cocoa beans are fermented in wooden boxes where autochthonous microorganisms (yeast, LAB and AAB) produce various metabolites, increase the temperature, decrease the cotyledon pH and trigger the formation of flavor precursors (Gutiérrez-Ríos, 2022)

Figure 2. World distribution of *T. cacao* (Criollo, Forastero and Trinitario) and *T. grandiflorum* (Cupuassu) (Jean-Marie, 2022)

is well established that agronomic and environmental conditions together with the harvest and post-harvest stages are the crucial elements in the determination of the final quality of the commercial grain (Forte, 2023); where the success of the commercialization is associated with the size and uniformity of the grain. The size of the cocoa bean plays a significant role in the structure, texture and flavor of the product. Small grains have a compact structure that leads to a higher concentration of aromas and flavors. Whereas, large grains fall apart easily during grinding, which produces a less consistent paste with less aroma. The size of the cocoa bean also influences the extraction of fatty acids; necessary to produce flavor. The quality of chocolate depends to a large extent on the quality of the cocoa bean used as raw material, and this involves evaluating certain morphological characteristics, such as length, width and weight of the bean, among other parameters. In the present investigation, an evaluation of the aforementioned characteristics was carried out, as well as a sample statistical analysis that allowed obtaining a size distribution profile of the grains of a hybrid variety between criollo cocoa and porcelain cocoa grown in the southern part of the lake, between 200-400 meters above sea level between the states of Mérida and Zulia, provided by a local supplier in the area.

Materials and methods

Characterization of the cocoa bean - Origin of the Seeds

The cocoa seeds used in this study were obtained from hybrid cocoa crops (porcelain and criollo) located in the southern area of Lake Maracaibo, in the surroundings of Santa Bárbara del Zulia, covering a wide area shared by the states of Zulia and Mérida, as shown in the satellite image

Sampling

A sample of ninety (90) previously fermented and dried cocoa beans was randomly taken to ensure a statistically valid sample size. Subsequently, we proceeded to determine the dimensions of length (major axis) and width (minor axis) in the selected grains. These measurements were made in triplicate using the ImageJ software, which allows estimating measurements with a high degree of precision. Then, each grain was weighed on an analytical balance, model: FA2004E, brand: W&J INSTRUMENT, with an appreciation of 0.0001g, which allowed obtaining the exact mass of each seed.

Results and discussions

Seed dimensions and weight

In order to carry out the statistical analysis of the cocoa beans, 50 beans were randomly chosen to measure the length and width, while 90 beans were taken for the weight, all this in order to verify that the distributions in both groups were normal.

The figure 4 shows the probability plot generated from the data on the weight of the cocoa beans, using the Minitab 20 program. It can be seen that the dispersion of data is maintained uniformly over most of the center line, thus as well as the value of the p statistic > 0.05 , which indicates that the

Figure 3. Satellite image of the cocoa production area between the States of Zulia and Mérida. Dotted area. (Taken from google maps)

Figure 4. Probability Plot for Cocoa seed weight data

distribution conforms to a normal model. On the other hand, the coefficient of the Anderson-Darling test is 0.532, which corroborates that the data fit a normal distribution model.

Figure 5. Probability plot for major axis length data in cocoa beans

The figures 5, 6 show the distribution of the data corresponding to the dimensions of the selected cocoa beans. The graph corresponding to the lengths of the major axis (Figure.5) shows a dispersion of the data along the center line,

Figure 6. Probability plot for minor axis length data in cocoa beans

which is indicative of a normal distribution, as indicated by the Anderson–Darling coefficient of 0.430, as well as the p -value > 0.05 , which confirms the assumption that the data fit this distribution model well. On the other hand, Figure 6 shows a behavior very similar to that reported in Figure 5. The data corresponding to the measurement of the length of the minor axis in the seeds were mostly dispersed along the central line; Similarly, the Anderson–Darling coefficient 0.324 and the $p > 0.05$ statistic show that the data satisfactorily fit a normal distribution model.

Table 1. Morphometric characteristics of the cocoa bean

Weight (g)*	Major axis length (cm)**	minor axis length (cm)**
1,5105 ± 0,2714	2,3590 ± 0,2259	1,3694 ± 0,1152

* N= 90 seeds

** N= 50 seeds

Figure 7. Histogram of normal distribution of the weight of the cocoa bean. (N=90)

In the figures 8 and 9 normal distribution histograms are shown for the major and minor axis length data, respectively, of cocoa beans. In both graphs it can be seen that the collected data conform to a normal or Gaussian distribution. This behavior was to be expected, since in the figures 4, 5 and 6, it was determined that the measurement data met the necessary requirements to adapt to a normal distribution.

Conclusions

- The hybrid cacao seeds from the southern area of the lake had an average weight of 1,5105 g ± 0,2714 g.

Figure 8. Histogram of normal distribution of the length of the major axis of the cocoa bean (N=50)

Figure 9. Histogram of normal distribution of the length of the minor axis of the cocoa bean (N=50)

- The average length and width of hybrid cocoa beans were 2,3590 cm ± 0,2259 cm and 1,3694 cm ± 0,1152 cm respectively.
- The distribution of weights and dimensions of the seeds were adjusted to normal or Gaussian distributions.

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